

Usability Evaluation of the Ministry of National Education Belgenet Correspondence System

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Abstract

The needs and innovations related to web technologies have manifested not only in the field of educational technologies but also in the management and operational processes, which are integral parts of the education system. The number of individuals and institutions benefiting from these technologies and innovations across various fields has steadily increased and continues to grow. One of the prominent concepts in ensuring that technology users with different roles and responsibilities derive maximum benefits from the technologies provided is usability. Accordingly, this study addresses the usability evaluation of the correspondence system, which constitutes a critical component of educational management processes. Between 2014 and May 2024, the Ministry of National Education (MoNE) utilized a desktop-based correspondence platform known as the Document Management System (DMS). In May 2024, due to specific needs and requirements, the ministry transitioned to the Belgenet correspondence system, a web-based application developed by Türksat under the Electronic Document Management System (EDMS) framework. The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the usability of the EDMS Belgenet correspondence system, which has been employed by the Ministry of National Education since 2024. The study seeks to reveal user satisfaction with the correspondence system and provide recommendations for addressing challenges encountered during its use. The research adopts a descriptive survey design as one of the quantitative research methods. The study's participants consist of five personnel from the Ministry of National Education holding various job titles. Data for the research were collected through authentic task tests and satisfaction surveys. Tasks were classified based on successful or unsuccessful outcomes. Following the authentic task test, satisfaction survey data were analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistics. The findings indicate that participants experienced difficulties in scenarios contradicting their previous correspondence system habits. While the satisfaction survey revealed appreciation for the aesthetic design, language, and learnability of the new system, it also highlighted the challenges in abandoning habits associated with the former correspondence system. However, the new web application demonstrated notable advantages over the previous desktop application, such as ease of access and task tracking via mobile devices. Additionally, the new system's ability to facilitate fast and uninterrupted communication was frequently emphasized. It is recommended that the Belgenet system incorporate detailed help menus, sections for frequently asked questions, and enhancements in feedback mechanisms to improve overall usability.

Keywords: Usability, Ministry Of National Education, Correspondence System, Belgenet, Ebys (Edms), Interface, Design

Öz

Web teknolojilerine ilişkin ihtiyaçlar ve yenilikler, yalnızca eğitim teknolojileri alanında değil, aynı zamanda eğitim sisteminin ayrılmaz bir parçası olan yönetim ve işleyiş süreçlerinde de kendini göstermiştir. Bu teknolojilerden ve yeniliklerden faydalanan birey ve kurum sayısı, farklı alanlarda giderek artmakta ve artış eğilimi devam etmektedir. Teknolojileri kullanan bireylerin farklı rol ve sorumluluklara sahip olmaları, sağlanan teknolojilerden azami düzeyde yarar sağlamalarını gerektirmektedir. Bu bağlamda, öne çıkan kavramlardan biri kullanılabilirliktir. Bu doğrultuda, söz konusu çalışma, eğitim yönetimi süreçlerinin önemli bir bileşeni olan yazışma sisteminin kullanılabilirlik değerlendirmesini ele almaktadır. Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı (MEB), 2014 yılından 2024 yılı Mayıs ayına kadar belge akış süreçlerinde Doküman Yönetim Sistemi (DYS) adlı masaüstü tabanlı bir yazışma platformunu kullanmıştır. Ancak 2024 yılı Mayıs ayında, belirli ihtiyaç ve gereklilikler doğrultusunda, Elektronik Belge Yönetim Sistemi (EBYS) çerçevesinde Türksat tarafından geliştirilen web tabanlı Belgenet yazışma sistemine geçiş yapılmıştır. Bu çalışmanın temel amacı, 2024 yılından itibaren MEB tarafından kullanılan EBYS Belgenet yazışma sisteminin kullanılabilirliğini değerlendirmek; sistemin kullanım sürecinde ortaya çıkan kullanıcı memnuniyetini ortaya koymak ve karşılaşılan sorunlara yönelik öneriler sunmaktır. Araştırma, nicel araştırma yöntemlerinden biri olan betimsel tarama modeli çerçevesinde desenlenmiştir. Çalışmanın katılımcılarını, Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı bünyesinde farklı unvanlara sahip beş personel oluşturmaktadır. Veriler, özgün görevler içeren testler ve memnuniyet anketi aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Görevler, başarılı ya da başarısız sonuçlara göre sınıflandırılmıştır. Özgün görev testi sonrasında uygulanan memnuniyet anketine ait veriler, betimsel istatistiklerle analiz edilerek yorumlanmıştır. Elde edilen bulgular, katılımcıların önceki yazışma sistemine dair alışkanlıklarıyla çelişen durumlarda zorlandıklarını ortaya koymuştur. Memnuniyet anketi sonuçları ise, yeni sistemin estetik tasarımı, dil kullanımı ve öğrenilebilirlik düzeyi açısından olumlu karşılandığını göstermiştir. Ancak, eski sistemden kaynaklanan alışkanlıkların terk edilmesinin zorluk oluşturduğu da vurgulanmıştır. Bununla birlikte, yeni web tabanlı uygulamanın masaüstü uygulamaya kıyasla mobil cihazlar üzerinden erişim kolaylığı ve görev takibine olanak sağlaması gibi belirgin avantajlar sunduğu görülmüştür. Ayrıca, sistemin hızlı ve kesintisiz iletişimi desteklemesi sıkça dile getirilen bir diğer olumlu yön olmuştur. Çalışma sonucunda, Belgenet sistemine kapsamlı yardım menülerinin, sıkça sorulan sorular (SSS) bölümlerinin ve geri bildirim mekanizmalarına yönelik iyileştirmelerin eklenmesi önerilmektedir. Bu tür düzenlemelerin, sistemin genel kullanılabilirliğini artıracığı düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Kullanılabilirlik, Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı (MEB), Yazışma Sistemi, Belgenet, Elektronik Belge Yönetim Sistemi (EBYS), Arayüz, Tasarım

1. Introduction

The importance of web-based systems belonging to government institutions has been increasing with the acceleration of digital transformation. Such systems provide information transmission to large masses of institutions while also increasing organizational efficiency by optimizing the flow of information within the institution (Ates & Karacan, 2009). Each web-based system has its own purpose and provides services to its users in line with this purpose (Soucy, 2007). Studies have emphasised that the usability of electronic document management systems significantly affects organisational efficiency and user satisfaction and emphasises the necessity of usability evaluations (Kutluturk & Ozdemirci, 2023). The interaction of these systems, which are developed to meet different needs, with the users is evaluated in the context of the usability of the system and in this context, the success of the system is closely related to the user experience (Yeniad, Mazman, Tuzun & Akbal, 2011). Moreover, usability assessments should extend beyond digital products, as the concept of usability has broader implications, including physical and urban environments, emphasizing its importance in multiple contexts (Cakici, Yilmaz, Karaman, Kursun & Simsek, 2017).

The main purpose of web-based systems is to enable users to complete certain tasks in the fastest and most trouble-free way. In this context, it is stated that the success and impact of systems can be explained largely by their usability (Soucy, 2007). Usability is a critical element in determining how efficiently, effectively and satisfactorily a system provides services to the user. In this context, the need to analyze users' interactions with the system with objective criteria has led to usability tests becoming a mandatory process (Tuzun, Telli, & Alir, 2016). These tests identify problems in the system, enable user-centered improvements, and make systems more effective.

Improving user experience is considered one of the cornerstones of the success of a web-based system. Systems that offer easier and more intuitive use increase users' loyalty to the system and increase their satisfaction levels (Pala, Arslan, & Özdiñç, 2017). For this reason, the development of user-friendly and highly usable designs is of great importance for the effective use of systems and their adoption by large masses (Ates & Karacan, 2009). Furthermore, the integration of generative artificial intelligence tools into educational and administrative processes introduces new user interaction expectations and challenges, emphasizing the importance of assessing users' emotional and perceptual experiences (Arslankara & Usta, 2024). In order to increase satisfaction with the use of web-based systems, it is of great importance to evaluate users' emotional well-being and digital satisfaction. Studies show that users' satisfaction in digital environments directly affects the overall system success (Arslankara, Demir, Oztas & Usta, 2022). In designing user-friendly digital systems, attention should be paid not only to functional aspects but also to core design principles such as alignment, simplicity, consistency, and balance, which directly influence user experience and satisfaction (Arslankara & Usta, 2020).

As Norman (2017) stated, everything man-made is a design product, and the quality of a design becomes apparent as a result of the interaction with the user. While a good design provides user satisfaction, a bad design becomes unusable and creates dissatisfaction and anger in the user. Therefore, a user-centered approach should be adopted in the design of web-based systems, and systems should be developed considering the interaction structure of technology with humans. Increasing the quality of design will both improve the user experience and increase the usage rates of the system. As a result, the usability of web-based systems is a factor that directly affects not only its technical performance, but also the users' approach to the system and their interaction with the system. Therefore, giving importance to usability tests in system design processes and making improvements based on user feedback will make the success of the systems sustainable.

In line with the circular published within the scope of the e-Correspondence Project carried out in our country, it has been made mandatory for public institutions and organizations to carry out their official correspondence through electronic document management systems (Official Gazette of the Republic of Turkey, 2017). The features that the document management systems of public institutions, organizations and private companies in Turkey must have are defined by the Product Certification (PC) given by the Turkish Standards Institute (TSI) within the scope of TS13298 Institutional Competence Assessment (ICA) (TSI, 2015). However, these standards are limited to the infrastructure, security and general functionality of the software used; they do not cover dimensions related to user experience such as usability, satisfaction and efficiency.

The spread of products that users encounter problems with during use or the continued preference of end users can create problems in this context. Therefore, it is of critical importance to ensure that any product offered for use is examined in terms of usability and that necessary improvements are made based on these examinations in order to ensure user satisfaction.

Especially when it is considered that the Ministry of National Education Electronic Document Management System (MoNE EDMS) Belgenet System was developed by MoNE and started to be used in all institutions after pilot applications, it becomes necessary to evaluate the system in terms of usability. However, as a result of the literature review, no study was found on the usability of MoNE EDMS Belgenet.

In this context, the aim of the study is to evaluate the usability of Belgenet (Electronic Document Management System), a correspondence application that the Ministry of National Education has started to use in its central and provincial organizations since 2024, to identify possible problems related to the use and design of the system and to offer solution suggestions. In this context, the main research question was determined as "What are the general usability problems experienced in the MoNE EDMS Belgenet interface during authentic tasks performed by system users and what could be the solution suggestions for these problems?"

Based on this main question, the following questions arise for Belgenet users:

- What are the task success rates of users for given tasks?
- What are the general satisfaction levels of users?

The study to be conducted in light of these questions is expected to contribute to the strengthening of Belgenet in terms of usability and making it a more user-friendly system. It will also provide concrete data for the redesign of electronic document management systems in a user-centered manner and for the more efficient use of the systems. Implementing improvement processes based on usability tests and user feedback in order to increase the performance of the system and user satisfaction also plays a critical role in the sustainable success of such projects.

2. Method

This study was conducted in the context of the usability and user satisfaction of the Ministry of National Education EdMS Belgenet system. The main purpose of the study is to evaluate the Belgenet system with a user-centered approach and to determine the usability level of the system. In this context, usability evaluation was carried out with usability testing, which is one of the user-centered evaluation techniques. This test method involves collecting data on the performance of a group representing the end users of the product while performing certain unique tasks on the system (Rubin, 1994).

In the study, the descriptive scanning method, one of the quantitative research approaches, was used. The descriptive scanning method is a method used to objectively reveal the current situation and was preferred to determine the difficulties, success rates and satisfaction levels of the participants while using the Belgenet system (Karasar, 2021). In this context, various measurement tools were used to evaluate both the usability of the system and the satisfaction of the users. Quantitative data were collected through

the task completion status and satisfaction survey conducted during the participants' interactions with the system. In a study in which the first author of the study was also involved (Yildiz, Arslankara, Karaman, Akbulut, & Tuzun, 2022), a usability study was conducted for the correspondence system used by the Ministry of National Education between 2012-2024. Therefore, in the first stage of this in-depth study, it was deemed sufficient to first consider the task completion status and satisfaction survey data. These data provide important clues in terms of understanding the functionality and user-friendliness of the system. The data obtained as a result of the research aimed to reveal in which areas the Belgenet system meets user needs and in which areas it needs to be developed.

Advanced usability testing techniques, such as eye-tracking methods, can provide deeper insights into how users interact with interfaces, uncovering subtle usability issues that traditional methods might miss (Yilmaz, Aygun, Akadal & Gulsecen, 2019)

2.1. Participants

Participants were selected on a voluntary basis from among school/institution principals, assistant principals, teachers and civil servants working in various institutions within the Ministry of National Education (MoNE). Regarding the number of participants used in the study, findings in the literature suggest that five participants would be sufficient to detect 85% of the usability problems of a product (Nielsen, 2000). Accordingly, a group of five people was formed within the scope of the study. Detailed demographic information about the participants is given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Participant	Age	Gender	Job Title	Professional Experience	Computer Usage Experience	Experience with MoNE Systems	Education Level
P1	42	Male	School Principal	25 years	25 years	10+ years	Bachelor's
P2	34	Female	Teacher	12 years	18 years	10+ years	Bachelor's
P3	39	Male	Assistant Principal	18 years	20 years	10+ years	Bachelor's
P4	27	Female	Civil Servant	10 years	15 years	7 years	Bachelor's
P5	37	Male	Assistant Principal	14 years	20 years	10+ years	Bachelor's

The age range of the participants ranged from 27 to 42, 2 were female and 3 were male. When examined in terms of professional experience, the participants' work experience ranged from 10 to 25 years. When looking at their level of education, it was determined that all participants had a bachelor's degree. In addition, the participants' computer usage experience ranged from 15 to 25 years. This situation shows that the participants' level of familiarity with technology was quite high.

When asked about their experiences with MoNE correspondence systems, one of the participants stated that they had 7 years of experience, while the other four participants stated that they had 10 years or more of experience. These long-term experience levels of the participants provided different perspectives in the usability evaluation of the system. This diversity contributed to a more comprehensive evaluation of the usability problems of the system. Finally, the demographic diversity of the participant group provided an important basis for understanding how the Belgenet system was experienced by different user profiles, and was a factor that increased the comprehensiveness and validity of the research.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

The data for the study were obtained from the participants' performance in completing authentic tasks during the application and from satisfaction surveys. Quantitative data revealed measurable aspects of the participants' interactions with the system, allowing the numerical evaluation of the application's effectiveness and user satisfaction.

2.2.1. Usability Test

The operations deemed critical for the usability test were determined by the researchers and presented to the opinions of 2 DMS experts, 2 EDMS Dcoumentnet experts and 1 field expert. A task list was created as a result of expert evaluations. Before the test, participants were informed about the tasks and permission was obtained for video-audio recording. The tests were conducted with each participant at different times, with the same computer and observer. The movements, images and sounds of the participants were recorded, and data on task completion status and duration were collected. In addition, the instructions on the tasks were given to the participants before the test.

2.2.2. Satisfaction Survey

After the literature review, the researchers prepared an 8-item satisfaction survey to evaluate the design of the Belgenet system, system language, speed, ease of learning, memorability of process steps and adequacy of warning messages. The survey draft was presented to field and system experts for their opinions, and the final version was given by making adjustments according to the suggestions. This satisfaction survey was applied to all participants after the usability test was completed. The difficulties and dissatisfaction that users experience when using document management systems may be related to their perception of trust and feelings of loneliness in digital environments. In this direction, it is also stated by previous studies that users' perceptions of trust towards systems can directly affect their overall satisfaction with system use (Arslankara & Usta, 2019).

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

The analysis of the research data began with the examination of the data obtained from the authentic tasks given to the participants. Authentic tasks were grouped as "rarely used" and "constantly used" operations according to their frequency of execution, and the analysis of the data was made according to this classification. The satisfaction survey data were evaluated with descriptive statistics and the participants' system satisfaction was revealed.

3. Findings

In this section, the answers to the research questions of the study are presented in the order of the research questions. The statistical analysis results of the data collected to address the sub-problems of the study and the interpretation of these results are included under the following headings.

3.1. Findings on Performing Authentic Tasks

The first research question is "What is the task success rate of users for given tasks?" In response to this question, task success rate and task completion times were evaluated with an authentic task test. During the usability test, the application screen was monitored by video and audio recording through a software. In the usability test, participants were asked to perform seven authentic tasks reflecting common usage

scenarios within the Belgenet system. These tasks included: (G1) creating a new official document, (G2) forwarding a received document to another user, (G3) searching for a previously created document, (G4) electronically signing a document, (G5) archiving completed documents, (G6) retrieving a mistakenly deleted document, and (G7) managing 24access permissions of documents. Task success rates and completion times for each participant are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.
Task Success Rate for Participants

Individuals	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 5	G 6	G 7	Number	Success %
1	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	4	57,1
2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	5	71,4
3	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	5	71,4
4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	6	85,6
5	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	6	85,6
Number of Success	4	5	4	5	3	2	3		
Success %	80	100	80	100	60	40	60		

When the participants' task success rates are examined, the participants with the highest success rate are the fourth and fifth participants; both participants successfully completed 85.6% of the tasks. The lowest success rate belongs to the first participant with 57.1%. When examined on a per-task basis, tasks G2 and G4 have the highest success rate, with all participants achieving 100% success in these tasks. In contrast, task G6 has the lowest success rate with 40%. In general, it is seen that the participants' success rates are around 68.5% on average. These results show that some tasks are more challenging than others, and the low success rate of task G6 in particular may suggest that the system is causing difficulties for users during this task.

3.2. Satisfaction Status Regarding Belgenet System

The second question of the research is "What is the general satisfaction level of the users?" The results of the descriptive analysis of the answers to the satisfaction survey questions regarding the Belgenet system are given in Table 3 below.

Table 3.
Distribution of Responses to the Satisfaction Survey

Items	f	%
1. General design features of the Belgenet system		
Bad	5	100
Neutral	0	0
Good	0	0
2. Belgenet system's language ...		
Not at all understandable	4	80
Partially understandable	1	20
Very understandable	0	0
3. Belgenet system's speed		
Slow	2	40

	Medium	3	60
	Fast	0	0
4.	Learning Belgenet system		
	Easy	4	80
	Medium	1	20
	Difficult	0	0
5.	Belgenet system process steps		
	Easy to remember	3	60
	Partly easy to remember	2	40
	Hard to remember	0	0
6.	Using the Belgenet system		
	Easy	1	20
	Medium	3	60
	Difficult	1	20
7.	When using the Belgenet system I feelphysically		
	Bad	0	0
	Nothing	5	100
	Good	0	0
8.	While using the Belgenet system I feel mentally		
	Bad	1	20
	Nothing	4	80
	Good	0	0

When the responses given to the satisfaction survey regarding the Belgenet system are examined, it is seen that all participants (100%) gave the answer “bad” regarding the general design features of the system. Regarding the system language, 80% of the participants evaluated the language as “not understandable at all” and 20% found it “partially understandable”. Regarding the system speed, 40% of the participants found the speed “slow” and 60% stated that it was “medium”. When asked about learning the Belgenet system, 80% of the participants stated that the system was “easy” to learn, while 20% stated that it was “medium”. Regarding the memorability of the process steps, 60% responded “easy to remember” and 40% responded “partially easy to remember”.

In response to the question evaluating the general use of the system, 20% of the participants evaluated the system as “easy”, 60% as “medium”, and 20% as “difficult”. In terms of physical sensations, all participants (100%) stated that they did not experience any physical effects during system use. Mentally, 80% of the participants stated that they “did not feel anything” and 20% stated that they “felt bad”. These findings show that the Documennet system could not provide user satisfaction in basic elements such as design and language, but was evaluated more positively in terms of learning and memorability of the process steps.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the usability, user experiences and satisfaction levels of the Belgenet (Electronic Document Management System) correspondence system, which the Ministry of National Education started to use in 2024, were examined. Belgenet has different features than the previous correspondence system, DMS (Document Management System), as it is a web-based application and stands out as a system where users experience both advantages and disadvantages in this respect.

As a result of Documennet's usability tests, it was observed that users experienced difficulties at the beginning, especially due to their habits to the old system. This result shows that, as in similar studies (for example, as seen in the DMS usability study), the system change requires a learning process based on habits on the users (Hook, 1997). Participants showed average success in terms of task completion rates, but the fact that some tasks (especially G6) had lower success rates revealed that the system made it difficult for users in these tasks. Another usability study conducted by the researchers was conducted

on the e-exam application. In this study, all participants completed all tasks completely and successfully (Arslankara, Arslankara, & Seferoglu, 2023).

Although Documennet's query functions have a more flexible and comprehensive structure compared to DMS, this can be complicated for some users. In the DMS usability study, it was observed that users had similar difficulties with query screens (Yildiz et al. 2022). This situation shows that Documennet's query menus should be made more intuitive (Nielsen, 1994). Findings of similar usability studies conducted on university websites reveal that design aesthetics, navigation, and accessibility are critical to user satisfaction, paralleling the issues identified in this study (Pehlivan Baskin, 2022).

In terms of user satisfaction, aspects of the Belgenet system such as aesthetic design and ease of learning were found positive by users. However, elements such as language use and speed were evaluated negatively, which reveals that the system needs to be improved in some areas. In the DMS study, it was also observed that participants found the system language understandable (Yildiz et al., 2022), but it is understood that Belgenet's more complex language structure has a negative impact on users (Pala et al., 2017).

Although Belgenet being web-based has provided advantages in terms of integration and access with mobile devices, it can be said that users do not have difficulty in remembering the steps in the system and are generally satisfied. However, dissatisfaction with speed indicates that improvements should be made regarding system performance (Ates & Karacan, 2009).

On the other hand, it is noteworthy that participants showed relatively high success rates in performing authentic tasks but expressed lower levels of overall satisfaction. In particular, negative evaluations regarding the general design and language of the system indicate that although users may functionally complete tasks, their experiences were negatively impacted by aesthetic and communicative aspects of the system. This reveals that technical task success alone may not ensure user satisfaction, and that usability evaluations should also prioritize emotional and perceptual dimensions of user experience. Additionally, difficulties adapting to the new system due to established habits from the previous system further highlight the discrepancy between success rates and satisfaction. Thus, these findings underscore the importance of addressing not only functionality but also emotional and aesthetic considerations in usability studies. Moreover, ensuring the usability and content quality of digital systems is critical, as these elements greatly influence users' trust and overall satisfaction (Celik, 2014).

Similarly, studies on generative artificial intelligence indicate that users' emotional and perceptual experiences significantly influence their interactions and success with technological systems, reinforcing the necessity of comprehensive usability assessments (Arslankara & Usta, 2024). Low user satisfaction with document management systems may be associated with the risks that users perceive in virtual environments. It is seen that the uncertainties experienced by users within the system may lead to mistrust and therefore dissatisfaction with the systems (Arslankara & Usta, 2019).

The following suggestions can be made to increase the usability of the Belgenet system and increase user satisfaction:

(i) In order to enable users to make more intuitive queries, it is recommended that query screens be simplified and guiding guides be added. (ii) In order for users to better understand the system language, the use of language should be simplified and warning messages that guide the user should be increased. (iii) Since increasing system speed is a factor that directly affects user satisfaction, it is important to make the necessary optimizations in this area. (iv) Clearer and more satisfactory feedback should be provided to users about the status of the transactions performed, and error messages should be more descriptive and solution-oriented.

In conclusion, the Documennet system offers some advantages as a web-based correspondence platform, but it needs improvements in certain areas to increase user experience and satisfaction. If the system is developed by taking into account the suggestions for the problems that emerged in the usability

tests, it will provide a more efficient and user-friendly experience in the correspondence processes of institutions within the Ministry of National Education. The inconsistency between the participants' task fulfilment rates and their overall satisfaction is consistent with the findings of other studies on the impact of digital environments on users' emotional well-being. In addition to the functional success of digital technologies, it is stated that the positive and negative emotional reactions of users should also be taken into consideration in system evaluations (Arslankara et al., 2022). Advanced usability testing techniques, such as eye-tracking methods, can provide deeper insights into how users interact with interfaces, uncovering subtle usability issues that traditional methods might miss (Yılmaz et al., 2019).

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